

Thermally Treated Asbestos–Cement Waste as a Low-Carbon Circular Cement: Effects on the Properties of Air-Cured Fiber Cement

CARNEIRO, Gessivaldo Oliveira¹; JOHN, Vanderley Moacyr²; DIAS, Cleber M. R.¹

¹Department of Materials Science and Technology / Federal University of Bahia, Rua Aristides Novis, 02. Federação, 40210-630 - Salvador/BA, Brazil.

²Department of Civil Engineering / University of São Paulo - Av Almeida Prado, trav. 2, n 87, Cidade Universitária, 05508-900 - Sao Paulo/SP, Brazil.

✉ gessivaldo19@outlook.com.

Abstract

Thermal treatment of asbestos-cement waste (ACW_{nat}) offers a pathway to produce a low-carbon circular binder (C^2BC), supporting circular-economy goals in the fiber-cement sector. This study assessed the use of C^2BC as a 25% partial replacement for Portland cement in fiber-cement boards and investigated its effects on matrix hydration kinetics (isothermal calorimetry and bound water) and on the physical and mechanical performance of the composites. The results show that C^2BC altered the hydration profile, shortening the setting time by 10% and increasing early-age reactivity. Despite a 18.4% reduction in the clinker factor, hydration efficiency remained comparable to that of the reference mixture, an advantageous outcome for formulations optimized for the Hatschek process. At the composite level, C^2BC did not increase drying shrinkage, reduced apparent density by approximately 5%, and delivered substantial mechanical improvements: +13% in modulus of rupture (MOR), and +50% in toughness, along with a 30% decrease in limit of proportionality (LOP). When MOR was normalized by clinker factor, performance increased by 67.5%, underscoring the high efficiency of this binder. Overall, incorporating C^2BC appears to be a promising strategy to reduce clinker demand, accelerate sector decarbonization, and valorize hazardous waste.

Keywords: Asbestos-cement waste, low-carbon circular cement, fiber cement, low clinker factor, thermal treatment.

1. Introduction

Given the recognized carcinogenic potential of asbestos fibers, more than 75 countries have banned asbestos mining, including Brazil in 2017 [1]. Between 1900 and 2015, over 210 Mt of asbestos were commercialized worldwide, generating more than 2.4 Gt of asbestos-based products [2]. In Brazil, processing of 8.8 Mt of chrysotile asbestos led to approximately 100 Mt of manufactured goods [3]. To mitigate this liability, several studies have evaluated different routes

for treatment and promoted the circularity of this waste [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. [12] highlight that thermal dihydroxylation represents the most effective strategy, albeit costly. Conversely, [3] proposed a solution that establishes optimal conditions for thermal treatment, minimizing CO₂ emissions and energy consumption while maximizing the crystallization of dicalcium silicate (α' -C₂S).

In this context, thermally treated asbestos-cement waste has been incorporated into the production of concrete [13], mortar [14], [15], [16], porcelain stoneware slabs [8], ceramic bricks [17], and in the production of geopolymers [18], [19] and alkali-activated materials [20]. However, no studies have yet specifically addressed its effects on the production of fiber-cement sheets. This strategy may promote a circular economy within the fiber cement sector by reintroducing this waste into the production cycle. Furthermore, considering the high cement content in fiber cement (up to 80% of the solid mass), the incorporation of supplementary cementitious materials becomes an effective strategy to reduce its environmental footprint [21], while potentially improving particle packing in low-carbon matrices [22]. However, the incorporation of reactive SCMs in the Hatschek process can increase water retention and promote the development of pathologies in fiber-cement artifacts. To address this challenge, this study investigates low-carbon circular cement (C²BC), a hydraulic binder produced by the thermal treatment of asbestos-cement waste, as a potential alternative for partial Portland cement replacement in fiber-cement sheets. The hydration mechanisms of C²BC-containing matrices were evaluated through heat flow, cumulative heat, and chemically bound water content, alongside the physical and mechanical properties of the resulting fiber-cement sheets.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Materials

To produce the composites, Portland cement CPII-F 40 (OPC, like CEM II), the low-carbon circular cement (C²BC) proposed by [3] was obtained by calcining asbestos-cement waste at 800 °C for 1 hour, limestone filler (LF), refined cellulose fiber (≈ 60 °SR), polypropylene fiber da Brasilit, and Hatschek process water were used. The specific density of OPC, limestone, and C²BC was determined using a helium pycnometer (AccuPyc II 1340, Micromeritics). The BET specific surface area (SSA) was determined by nitrogen adsorption, and the particle size distribution was measured by laser diffraction (Sympatech Helos KR). The shape factor, which assesses particle sphericity, was calculated as the ratio of the BET surface area to the theoretical surface area (laser diffraction) [23], with values close to 1 indicating spherical particles [24]. The volumetric specific surface area (VSA_{BET}) was obtained by multiplying the BET_{SSA} and specific density. As shown in Table 1, C²BC has the highest shape factor, indicating a larger contact area with water. This will require more water to lubricate the particles and reduce friction. This high shape factor, combined with its larger BET_{SSA} (due to angular morphology or porosity), may affect the flocculation system and lead to pathologies. In contrast, limestone filler, the main inert supplementary cementitious

material (SCM) used in the Hatschek process, exhibited a shape factor closer to spherical, which is ideal for improved particle packing in fiber-cement products.

Table 1 – Physical properties of selected raw materials.

Materials	ρ (g/cm ³)	SSADL (m ² /g)	SSABET (m ² /g)	VSA _{BET} (m ² /cm ³)	D ₁₀ (μ m)	D ₅₀ (μ m)	D ₉₀ (μ m)	Shape factor
OPC	3.12	1.04	1.55	4.84	2.93	12.89	34.45	4.66
LF	2.76	0.70	0.55	1.52	4.63	21.79	53.87	2.15
C ² BC	2.97	1.09	7.68	22.81	2.53	12.00	74.88	20.85

The chemical composition of the materials was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) using a Malvern Panalytical Zetium spectrometer. As shown in Table 2, OPC meets the requirements established by NBR 16697 (ABNT, 2018), with a carbonate content of 11.2%, determined by loss on ignition via stoichiometric calculation, and SO₃ content below 4.5%. C²BC, in turn, is composed mainly of CaO, SiO₂, and MgO, associated with the cementitious matrix and the anhydrous magnesium silicate inherent to the dehydroxylation of chrysotile [Mg₃Si₂O₅(OH)₄]. Analysis of the limestone filler indicates a calcitic composition, based on CaO and MgO contents.

Table 2 – Chemical composition of materials, in the form of oxides (wt. %).

Materials	CaO	SiO ₂	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	Others	LOI ¹
OPC	64.80	13.30	4.91	3.50	3.53	3.38	0.82	0.12	0.70	4.94
LF	53.10	0.63	0.74	1.31	0.23	0.06	0.00	0.06	1.20	42.67
C ² BC	45.09	18.54	6.57	2.83	4.29	1.70	0.32	0.24	1.29	19.13

¹ Loss on ignition at 1020 °C.

Furthermore, the mineralogical composition was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer with a copper tube (Cu K α) operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. Data were collected over a 2 θ range of 5° to 75° in continuous mode, with a step size of 0.02°, a step time of 300 seconds, and an area detector. Crystalline phases were quantified using Panalytical X'Pert HighScore Plus software (version 4.9) and the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD). The amorphous content was estimated with the internal standard method using lithium fluoride (LiF). Table 3 presents the mineralogical composition of the raw materials determined by the Rietveld method. Chrysotile was not detected in C²BC treated at 800 °C. The formation of dicalcium silicate (α' _H-C₂S) at low temperature can be attributed to the decomposition of C-S-H (calcium silicate hydrate), due to its high surface area and refinement of the size of the crystallites present in cementitious fines waste [25]. The calcitic nature of the limestone filler was validated by both XRF and XRD. The RWP and GOF indicators confirm the reliability of the refinement [26].

To evidence the morphological changes in asbestos fibers, a microstructural analysis was performed on a fractured section of an asbestos-cement roofing tile using a field emission gun scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM), FEI Inspect F50 (15–20 kV, 0.96 mA). Figure 1a shows

fibrous asbestos bundles distributed within the cementitious matrix, similar to those observed by [38], [39], [40]. In contrast, Figure 3b presents the microstructure of C²BC. For [5], chrysotile microfibrils irreversibly lose their flexibility and original morphology due to dehydroxylation, becoming brittle. In this process, pseudomorphosis is characterized by the replacement of the original fibrous cleavage by a three-dimensional intergrowth of subspherical forsterite crystals [7]. This rearrangement preserves the material's circular morphology but irreversibly alters its molecular composition and mechanical properties. On the other hand, the Hatschek process water was chemically characterized. The elemental composition, determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES; Horiba Ultima Expert), was as follows: Ca (686 mg/l), K (10.81 mg/l), Na (1.63 mg/l), and Si (1.30 mg/l). The soluble sulfate concentration (SO₄²⁻), measured by the gravimetric method (NBR 15900-7), was 12.86 mg/l. The water pH, determined at 23 °C following the NBR 15903-3 method, was 13.

Table 3 – Mineralogical composition of raw materials obtained using the Rietveld method.

Phases	OPC	LF	C ² BC	ICSD code	Reference
C ₃ S-M ₃	59.79	0.00	0.00	94742	[27]
b-C ₂ S	4.80	0.00	6.69	81096	[28]
α _H -C ₂ S	0.00	0.00	18.14	81097	[28]
C ₃ A - Cubic	5.00	0.00	0.00	1841	[29]
C ₄ AF	6.43	0.00	6.47	9197	[30]
Gypsum	3.91	0.00	0.00	151692	[31]
Periclase	4.23	0.00	6.98	9863	[32]
Portlandite	1.13	0.00	3.41	15471	[33]
Anhydrite	0.00	0.00	1.95	1956	[34]
Calcite	11.15	83.21	9.14	79673	[35]
Quartz	0.61	0.89	1.42	200721	[36]
Dolomite	1.02	2.13	0.00	31209	[37]
Amorphous content + unidentified	2.35	13.78	31.35	-	-
GOF	3.35	1.43	2.46	-	-
RWP	9.33	9.05	7.64	-	-

Figure 1 - Micrograph of the fracture section of the residue (a) in situ and (b) after heat treatment at 800°C.

2.2. Effect of dilution on matrix hydration kinetics

A cement–water paste with a water-to-solid ratio of 0.5 was used as the reference mixture (REF). Pastes containing cement + limestone filler + water and cement + C²BC + water were also evaluated. In both formulations, 25% of the cement (by mass) was replaced with limestone filler or C²BC, respectively. The evaluation included isothermal calorimetry and the quantification of bound water over time.

Hydration heat flow and Bound water and portlandite content

To isolate the effect of the additions on the heat of hydration, three pastes were prepared: a reference paste (OPC) and two binary pastes in which OPC was diluted with limestone filler and C²BC. The heat of hydration and its release rate were determined using an isothermal calorimeter (Calmetrix I-Cal 8000 HPC) at 23 °C. Each test used 50.0 g of anhydrous cementitious material and 25.0 g of process water, both weighed to ±0.001 g. Sample preparation followed ASTM C1702-23, with a total of 60 seconds: water addition (5 s), manual mixing with a spatula (45 s), and initiation of measurement immediately after homogenization (10 s). Heat release was monitored for 168 h.

To evaluate the effects of limestone filler and C²BC on bound water content, the pastes were prepared in three stages: i) water addition to the powder within 5 s; ii) manual mixing with a spoon for 50 s; and iii) dispersion using a high-energy rotary mixer (Makita, model RT0700C) at 10,000 rpm for 90 s. [41] details the procedure for specimen molding, curing, and hydration stoppage by solvent exchange. The chemically bound water content (C_w) in the mixtures was quantified by thermogravimetric analysis (Netzsch T209 F1 Libra) using an alumina crucible with 50 mg of sample, a heating rate of 20 °C/min, and an inert nitrogen atmosphere (N₂) up to 1000 °C. From the mass loss curves, the C_w and portlandite (CH) contents were calculated according to Equations 1 and 2, following the methodology described by [42]. Where: M is the molar mass, and W_x is the percentage of mass loss at temperature x °C. Furthermore, to correct the portlandite content due to overlap with the mass loss associated with calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H), the tangent method was adopted[43].

$$C_w = \left(\frac{W_{40} - W_{550}}{W_{550}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$CH = \left(\frac{W_{450} - W_{550}}{W_{550}} \right) \times \frac{M[Ca(OH)_2]}{M(H_2O)} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

2.3. Study on the interaction of additions in fiber cement boards

Fiber cement sheets were molded using a methodology that simulates the Hatschek process, with a sequential filtration and compaction system proposed by [44]. To evaluate the effect of C²BC, a reference formulation with fixed contents of cement (OPC), limestone filler (LF), polypropylene fibers, and cellulose was established, with OPC being partially replaced by C²BC, as shown in Table

4. To produce the fiber-cement sheets (200×200×6) mm³, the following protocol was adopted: (i) dispersion of polypropylene fibers in process water (600 rpm, 120 s); (ii) addition of refined cellulose and solid components, with homogenization (600 rpm, 120 s); (iii) pouring the suspension into the mold and vacuum filtration (400 mmHg, 6 min) on filter paper (80 g/m²). It should be noted that this method does not reproduce critical operational variables of the industrial Hatschek process.

Table 4 – Standard formulation adopted to produce fiber cement.

Formulation	Composition (% by mass)				
	OPC	C ² BC	LF	PP + Cellulose	Process water (g/l)
OPC+LF (reference)	73.40	0.00	21.70	4.90	200
OPC+LF+C ² BC	55.05	18.35	21.70	4.90	200

After filtration, the surface of the fresh mat was leveled using a flat, rectangular metal tamper. Subsequently, a sequential load was applied in a hydraulic press (15 t capacity) with the following pressure stages: 0.49 MPa (30 s), 0.98 MPa (30 s), 1.47 MPa (30 s), and 1.96 MPa (90 s), simulating the progressive compaction of the Hatschek process. After pressing, the sheets were sealed with plastic film and subjected to thermal curing in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h (Quimis, model Q316M).

Characterization of composites

The physical properties (apparent density, water absorption, and apparent porosity) of each formulation were determined in accordance with NBR 15210-2 (ABNT, 2023). Four-point flexural strength was measured using an Instron universal testing machine (model 5569) with a 1 kN load cell at a loading rate of 5 mm/min. The modulus of rupture (MOR), limit of proportionality (LOP), modulus of elasticity (MOE), and specific energy (EE) were determined according to Equations 3–6 [45]. EE was obtained from the area under the load versus deflection curve up to the maximum load (MOR). Five replicates per formulation were evaluated after 10 days of curing.

$$MOR = \frac{P_{max} \cdot L}{b \cdot e^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$LOP = \frac{P_{LOP} \cdot L}{b \cdot e^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

$$MOE = \frac{L^3 \cdot 23}{1296 \cdot I} \left(\frac{P}{\delta} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

$$EE = \frac{A_P - \delta}{b \cdot e} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Where: **P**_{max} is the maximum test load (N), **L** is the distance between supports (mm), **b** is the specimen width (mm), **e** is the specimen thickness (mm), **P/δ** is the angular slope of the elastic region of the load versus deflection curve (N/mm), **I** is the moment of inertia of the cross section,

given by $(b \cdot e^3/12)$ in mm^4 , $\mathbf{Ap-\delta}$ is the total area under the load versus deflection curve (N.mm), $\mathbf{P_{LOP}}$ is the maximum load in the linear region.

Drying shrinkage was also analyzed as described by Souza [46], by monitoring dimensional variation over 28 days. After thermal curing, the sheets were conditioned in a moist chamber ($23\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} > 90\%$, 72 h), sectioned into four specimens ($40 \times 160 \times 6$) mm^3 per formulation, and reconditioned for 48 h. During this period, concave-conical metal pieces were fixed to the ends with instant adhesive. After 6 days of moist curing, drying shrinkage was determined using a measuring frame equipped with a digital dial gauge (precision: 0.001 mm), calibrated with an Invar standard (160 mm). The initial reading, taken before drying, established the baseline. The specimens were dried in a climatic chamber ($23\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 50% RH; Thermotron SM-3.5S) (Souza, 2014). Mass loss over time was also estimated using an analytical balance (resolution: 0.01 g) after each dimensional measurement.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Effects of C²BC and limestone on the reactivity of mixtures

Analysis of the heat flow curve (Figure 2a) shows that the dilution effect is evident in mixtures containing a limestone filler and C²BC, compared with the reference (OPC) and its pure dilution (75% OPC). As expected, OPC, with its higher content of reactive phases ($\text{C}_3\text{S} + \text{C}_3\text{A} = 68.50\%$), exhibits the most intense heat peak. However, when partially replaced by C²BC, heat flow increases relative to the pure dilution curve, indicating an accelerating effect on hydration kinetics. This behavior is attributed to the high specific surface area of C²BC and the reactivity of its dehydrated products. In the early stages, the shorter induction period is attributed to the partial rehydration of C-S-H and ettringite in the mixture containing the residues [47]. Additionally, the presence of $\alpha'_\text{H-C}_2\text{S}$, a more reactive phase than $\beta\text{-C}_2\text{S}$, may contribute to hydration at later ages [25].

The mixture containing C²BC displays a secondary exothermic peak following the main silicate peak. This phenomenon is associated with sulfate depletion in solution, thereby shifting the equilibrium toward further ettringite formation. The dissolution of residual C_3S and C_3A from OPC, combined with ions released by C²BC, provides Ca^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} for ettringite precipitation [48]. The presence of carbonates, as in the limestone filler mixture, led to the formation of a secondary exothermic peak at around 20 h, indicative of hemicarboaluminate precipitation [49]. Although [50], [51] report that inert SCMs accelerate C_3S hydration by acting as nucleation sites, thereby increasing the C-S-H precipitation rate, combined with the additional space generated by dilution, did not result in increased heat flow during the acceleration phase when compared to the pure dilution curve (Figure 2a). Nevertheless, the formation of AFm phases and greater hydrate precipitation increased chemically bound water at 1, 7, and 28 days relative to pure dilution, as shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2b shows that the chemically bound water content per 100 g of cement was highest in OPC, owing to its greater formation of hydrated products. However, in the mixture containing C²BC, the bound water content after 24 hours was comparable to that of the reference, highlighting the high early reactivity of this residue, which accelerated hydration kinetics and ettringite precipitation. Despite this, at 7 and 28 days, the bound water content in the C²BC mixture remained lower than that of OPC. A 12% increase in portlandite content was observed in the mixture containing C²BC after 24 h and a 7% increase after 28 days, compared with the pure dilution, attributable to hydration. It is worth noting that the pure dilution curve corresponds to 75% of the flow released in the OPC mixture. Table 5 presents the parameters obtained from the heat flow curves, including: induction period (IP); Peak_{max} extracted from silicate and aluminate reactions; setting time (ST) according to ASTM C1679-17; and cumulative heat released after 12, 24, and 72 hours (H12, H24, and H72), respectively.

Table 5 –Parameters obtained from isothermal calorimetry curves.

Mixture	IP _{ini} ^a (h)	IP _{fin} ^b (h)	Peak _{max} ^c (mW/g)	ST ^d (h)	H12 ^e (J/g)	H24 ^f (J/g)	H72 ^g (J/g)
OPC	0.66	3.56	4.63	5.78	114.56	248.45	338.56
OPC+LF	0.57	3.72	3.34	5.80	86.00	186.40	280.00
OPC+LF+C ² BC	1.36	2.84	3.96	5.20	106.40	209.02	296.00

In this context, partial replacement of OPC with C²BC resulted in higher heat flow than inert dilution at the same clinker content. In the Hatschek process, where the heat of hydration plays a key role in product formation and demolding, this behavior indicates that C²BC may enable replacement levels exceeding 25% without compromising, and potentially even accelerating, early-age kinetics, thereby improving production-cycle efficiency in low-carbon formulations.

Figure 2 - Effect of dilution on heat flow obtained in isothermal calorimetry (a) and chemically bound water determined by mass loss in thermogravimetry.

3.2. Effect of the clinker factor on the physical properties of composites

To evaluate the contribution of C²BC to fiber-cement, a standard industrial formulation that already incorporates SCM was used. In the reference composite with limestone filler, water

absorption was $25.36 \pm 0.59\%$, apparent density was $1.50 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and apparent porosity was $38.04 \pm 0.92\%$. These values reflect the physical filling effect provided by the filler, whose more spherical shape (shape factor = 2.15) promoted better particle packing, reduced macropore volume, and densified the matrix at a clinker factor of 62.17%. In contrast, the mixture containing C²BC exhibited higher water absorption ($27.55 \pm 0.66\%$) and lower apparent density ($1.43 \pm 0.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$), resulting in an apparent porosity of $39.46 \pm 0.58\%$. This increase in porosity can be attributed to the higher shape factor of C²BC (20.85), which hinders particle packing and favors a more porous microstructure as the clinker factor decreases to 43.82%.

Analysis of Figure 3 shows that the increase in apparent porosity and the decrease in clinker factor in the ternary system with C²BC did not result in greater drying shrinkage. This suggests that the extra porosity caused by the irregular shape of C²BC (high shape factor, as shown in Table 1) increased the volume of macropores ($>0.05 \mu\text{m}$), which are less affected by capillary stresses. According to [46], the capillary pore fraction (gel and mesopore range, 2.5 nm to $0.05 \mu\text{m}$) is important for significantly increasing capillary stresses. This demonstrates that, with respect to drying shrinkage, the type and distribution of pores are more important than the total pore volume.

The drying kinetics and mass loss described in Figure 3 show two clear stages: (I) during the first four days, most of the mass loss (about 93%) and 80% of the drying shrinkage at 28 days occur. This is due to the rapid evaporation of free water, which increases capillary stresses and causes drying shrinkage; (II) afterward, there is a sharp decrease in mass loss and shrinkage rates, indicating that the system gradually reaches equilibrium with the environment and evaporation is then controlled by internal moisture diffusion. It is also important to note that, for the mixture containing C²BC, accelerated hydration did not result in additional gel pore formation. This confirms that the porosity created by C²BC retained a pore structure similar to that of the reference binary system, with pores that are less affected by capillary stresses and therefore do not contribute to increased drying shrinkage at a clinker factor of 43.82%.

Figure 3 – Effect of C²BC on drying shrinkage (a) and mass loss (b) as a function of drying time.

3.3. Mechanical properties of composites

The incorporation of C²BC significantly modified the composite's mechanical properties (Table 6). Increases of 13% in modulus of rupture (MOR), 24% in modulus of elasticity (MOE), and 50% in specific energy (EE) were observed, alongside a 30% reduction in the limit of proportionality (LOP). This profile characterizes pseudo-ductile behavior, with greater deformation capacity and energy absorption prior to failure. The reduction in LOP indicates early onset of microcracking, even in a matrix with increased stiffness. This effect is attributed to the thermal activation of the residue at 800 °C, which completely dehydrated the C-S-H and promoted the crystallization of hydraulic phases, such as α' H-C₂S. Upon contact with water, the dehydrated C-S-H partially rehydrates, such as α' H-C₂S [25]. Upon contact with water, partial rehydration of C-S-H and ettringite occurs [47], while the newly formed α' H-C₂S undergoes hydration, with both processes contributing to the overall hydration reaction. Furthermore, the combination of initial stiffness with early yielding suggests that internal stress redistribution occurs, initiating microcracking at lower loads. This is a beneficial mechanism that may relieve internal stresses and reduce cracking. [46], as evidenced by the drying shrinkage curve illustrated in Figure 3. Thus, the resulting microstructure facilitated post-peak energy dissipation mechanisms, such as crack deflection and anchoring, reinforced by a fiber-matrix interface more resistant to pull-out.

In this context, the synergy between the densified matrix and the consolidated fiber-matrix interface enabled efficient stress redistribution and delayed fracture propagation. To quantify binder efficiency, MOR was normalized by clinker content. In the composite containing C²BC, the MOR/clinker ratio was 19.40 MPa per 100% clinker, surpassing the reference value (10.97 MPa per 100% clinker) by 56.54%. This behavior confirms the high reactivity of the thermally activated binder, demonstrating the technical feasibility of substantially reducing the clinker factor in fiber-cement sheets produced via the Hatschek process without compromising mechanical performance. This strategy is therefore aligned with the sector's decarbonization and circular economy goals.

Figure 4 – Mechanical properties of fiber cement boards with OPC plus limestone filler (a), and OPC with limestone filler and C²BC (b), highlighting the confidence interval ($\alpha=0.05$), with 10 days of curing.

Table 6 – Mechanical properties of composites at 28 days, indicating standard deviation.

Mixture	Clinker factor (%)	MOR/clinker ratio (MPa)	MOR (MPa)	LOP (MPa)	MOE (MPa)	EE (kJ/mm ²)
OPC+LF	62.17	10.97	7.35 ± 0.42	5.28 ± 0.74	7.03 ± 0.84	2.58 ± 1.04
OPC+LF +C ² BC	43.82	19.40	8.50 ± 0.62	3.67 ± 0.47	9.25 ± 1.01	5.13 ± 1.24

4. Conclusions

The incorporation of C²BC as a partial replacement for Portland cement in fiber cement sheets proved to be an effective strategy for reducing the clinker factor below 40% without compromising product performance, as evidenced by:

- The dilution of OPC with C²BC altered hydration kinetics, accelerating heat flow and reducing setting time by 10%, with higher chemically bound water content within the first 24 hours compared to the reference. This behavior may be advantageous for the Hatschek process, enabling shorter production cycles in low-clinker formulations.
- The 6% increase in total porosity induced by C²BC did not amplify drying shrinkage. This indicates that the introduced porosity is likely within the macropore range (>0.05 μm) and therefore does not generate critical capillary stresses. This finding reinforces that pore size distribution is a more critical parameter than total pore volume for crack control.
- The C²BC-containing sheets promoted microstructural refinement and strengthening of the fiber-matrix interface. This optimization resulted in a superior mechanical profile, with increases of 13% in MOR, 24% in MOE, and 50% in specific fracture energy, despite a 30% reduction in the limit of proportionality.
- Clinker efficiency analysis showed that the composite containing C²BC exhibited a 56.54% increase in specific strength (MOR/clinker), confirming the high hydraulic reactivity of the thermally activated binder.

In summary, C²BC establishes itself as a technically and environmentally viable alternative for fiber-cement production. The use of this binder enables optimization of mechanical properties without increasing drying shrinkage, while reducing clinker consumption, contributing to the sector's decarbonization, and aligning with circular economy principles, in addition to adding value to hazardous waste.

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